

resistance or susceptibility to gall midge or recording midge infestation and parasitization in the field often do not record infestation and parasitization of suppressed galls.

To estimate the proportion of exposed and suppressed galls in the infested hills, 20 random hills of Jaya in the vegetative stage were dissected every 2 weeks for 3 years and 7,541 galls were tested to determine the parasitization percentage in exposed versus suppressed galls.

There was a 4:1 ratio of exposed to suppressed galls (Fig. 1). Parasitization in the suppressed galls was higher during early Apr, May, and Jun, late Jan and Mar, and in Jul (Fig. 2). □

2. Parasitization of galls by *Platygaster oryzae*.

Thaia subrufa (Homoptera:Cicadellidae) occurrence in Karnataka, India

Gavi Gowda, K. R. Jayaram, and Nagaraju, Regional Research Station, University of Agricultural Sciences, Mudigere - 577132, Karnataka, India

Thaia leafhoppers are becoming serious pests of cereals, especially rice. *Thaia oryzivora* Ghauri and *T. subrufa* (Motschulsky) cause substantial damage to rice in several Asian countries.

In Feb 1978, *T. subrufa* adults and nymphs were found in large numbers on leaf blades of rice seedlings in summer crop nurseries in Mudigere. Infestation persisted, even on transplanted rice plants, in Mar-Apr 1978 and caused hopperburn symptoms in some plots. Panicle size in affected plots was considerably reduced. Leafhopper populations were so high that 150 to 200 adults were col-

lected in each sweep of a 25-cm diameter insect net. The ratio of males to females ranged from 1:1.20 to 1:2.06 in different months.

Adults and nymphs usually sucked on the leaf undersurface, causing white specks on the upper surface, which often ran into zigzag lines. The specks later turned brown and gave the plants a burnt appearance. When enclosed on rice plants in the laboratory, a single adult damaged a 1-cm² area a day. Preliminary biological observations show that the nymphal period lasts 23-25 days and has 5 instars, and that adults live 33-45 days.

Pest activity in the rice fields has been monitored since 1978. Although found throughout the year, the pest bred actively Oct-May and severely damaged the summer crop. Light trap catches of adults are shown in the table. The pest was also seen on several grass weeds and on finger millet *Eleusine coracana* Gaertn.

Light trap catches of *Thaia subrufa* in Karnataka, India.

Month	Leafhoppers (no.) ^a	
	1981	1982
Jan	577	205
Feb	635	145
Mar	287	59
Apr	175	231
May	92	168
Jun	4	2
Jul	0	2
Aug	-	-
Sep	0	-
Oct	16	3
Nov	164	193
Dec	246	99

^a - = no observation.

Dimethoate, methyl parathion, and quinalphos at 0.05% spray effectively controlled the pest. Leafhopper populations also declined after a heavy rain. □

Effect of nitrogen and plant density on rice stem borer infestation in Western Kenya

D. T. Ho, entomologist, and J. G. Kibuka, technician, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, P.O. Box 30772, Nairobi, Kenya

A survey of rice ecosystems in Kenya showed that rice farmers grow rice in low-fertility swamps at high plant density (about 1 million hills/ha at 10- × 10-cm

spacing) because they believe higher plant populations will produce higher yields.

We studied the effect of plant density and fertility on insect infestation in field trials at Mbita Point, in western Kenya, under swampy lowland conditions. Sindano, a traditional rice variety, was grown on black cotton soil (saline phase, gleyic solonetz) composed of 40% sand, 14% silt, and 46% clay. Rice was planted at 10- × 20- and 20- × 20-cm spacing for populations of 500,000 and 250,000 hills/ha. Nitrogen was applied at

0,60, and 120 kg/ha at land preparation with 30 kg P and 50 kg K/ha. The predominant rice insect was stem borer. No disease was observed.

Results showed that stem borer damage was the same for crops at different plant densities, except at 120 kg N/ha. Deadhearts were caused by *Diopsis* spp. and whiteheads by *Sesamia calamistis*.

Infestation by combined *S. calamistis* and *Maliarpha separattella* did not differ among treatments (see table), but percentage of empty grains was significant.

antly related to the level of stem infestation by *M. separata*. Although stem infestation was similar among treatments, the percentage of empty grains was significantly higher at higher N levels.

Yield was relatively low because of low soil fertility. Analysis of number of productive tillers per unit area indicates that the high density crop produced many panicles/m² but few grains/panicle. Yield did not increase with plant population, and seed costs and labor costs for transplanting were higher. High density planting was not economically viable. □

Effect of fertility and plant density on stem borer infestation and rice yield in Western Kenya.^a

	500,000 hills/ha			250,000 hills/ha		
	0 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha
Hills with deadhearts ^b (%)	2.8 a	3.5 ab	8.5 b	5.3 ab	6.2 ab	15.4 c
Hills with whiteheads ^c (%)	1.9 a	4.0 ab	7.0 b	4.8 ab	9.2 bc	15.2 c
Stem infestation ^c (%)	70.0 a	72.0 a	74.0 a	73.0 a	81.0 a	83.0 a
Empty grains (%)	2.6 a	2.7 ab	4.9 c	2.4 a	2.8 b	4.1 c
Panicles/m ²	352 b	392 c	477 d	242 ab	201 a	330 b
Grains/panicle	108 a	107 a	111 a	313 b	315 b	359 b
Yield (t/ha)	1.9 a	1.9 ab	1.9 b	1.9 b	2.0 c	2.0 d

^aMeans in a row followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bDeadhearts and whiteheads were counted 60 and 120 days after transplanting, respectively. ^cRecorded at harvest.

Stem borers in various rice ecosystems in Kenya

D. T. Ho, entomologist, and J. G. Kibuka, technician, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, P.O. Box 30772, Nairobi, Kenya

We surveyed incidence of stem borers, a serious rice pest in some Kenyan ecosystems. Rice is grown on small farms and in irrigated lowlands, rainfed uplands, and swamplands.

Lowland irrigated rice is the most important ecosystem, being a monoculture in areas of several thousand hectares. Upland rainfed rice is grown in small areas and rotated with maize or sorghum during the long rainy season. Swampy lowland rice is grown on marginal swampland in western Kenya where water can be 30 cm deep and tall varieties are planted.

Lepidopterous borers present are *Chilo partellus*, *Sesamia calamistis*, and *Maliarpha separata*. The first two species are major pests of sorghum and maize and *M. separata* is specific to rice. Dipterous borers are *Diopsis thoracica* and *D. apicalis*.

The survey included the western, central, and coastal provinces. At each location rice stalks at various growth stages were dissected. Infestation was recorded as percentages of hills and tillers

Stem borer incidence in various rice ecosystems in Kenya.

Rice ecosystem	Year	Hills infested (%)	Tillers infested (%)	Stem borers/hill (no.) ^a				Species composition (%)			
				C	D	M	S	C	D	M	S
Lowland irrigated (2 locations)	1981	95	41	0	0	4.5	.2	0	0	90	10
	1982	72	10	0	.3	.3	0	0	52	48	0
	Mean	83	25.5	0	.15	2.4	.1	0	26	69	5
Upland rainfed (6 locations)	1981	62	14	.1	.01	.1	0	50	6	44	0
	1982	16	8	.5	.05	.15	.1	12	32	44	12
	Mean	39	11.0	.3	.03	.12	.05	31	19	44	6
Swampy lowland (3 locations)	1982	53	5	0	.9	0	0	0	100	0	0
Flooded swamp (1 location)	1981	56	12	0	0	.8	0	0	0	100	0

^aC = *Chilo partellus*, D = *Diopsis* spp.; M = *Maliarpha separata*, S = *Sesamia calamistis*.

infested. Species composition and average number of larvae, pupae, and pupal cases recovered per hill were recorded (see table).

Stem borer infestation generally was higher in lowland irrigated rice, with *M. separata* predominating. *M. separata* also infested flooded swamp rice, where other stem borers were absent. It damaged the crop at all growth stages and caused a large proportion of unfilled grains. *Diopsis* occurred more frequently in lowlands where water is available, but was not found in flooded swamps. It infested rice only at early vegetative phase

and caused characteristic deadhearts. Upland rainfed rice was infested more by sorghum and maize pests — *C. partellus* and *S. calamistis* — than lowland rice.

Different stem borer species and damage levels in various rice ecosystems require different control methods. Yield obtained from ecosystems other than lowland irrigated rice is low, making chemical control uneconomical. For upland rice, however, yield-improving practices such as crop rotation or intercropping with a leguminous crop tends to reduce stem borer population while increasing soil fertility. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tales, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.